

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

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IMPLEMENTING SMOKING CESSATION INTERVENTIONS
FOR PREOPERATIVE PATIENTS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Background: In the preoperative setting, providers inevitably encounter patients with a smoking history. In the U.S., an estimated 8 to 10 million surgical procedures requiring anesthesia are performed annually on cigarette smokers (Mills et al., 2011). Cigarette smoking has negative health implications for surgical patients to include cardiovascular, pulmonary, and wound healing complications which can result in sequelae such as reintubation, wound dehiscence, and increased length of stay. Smoke cessation prior to any kind of surgery reduces complications, however, information on the effects of smoking and benefits of smoking cessation on surgical outcomes are not regularly provided to patients (Khullar & Maa, 2012; Lauerman, 2008). Additionally, nearly half of surgeons do not regularly provide information or suggest interventions about smoke cessation prior to surgery (Khullar & Maa, 2012). Therefore, the preoperative setting presents an excellent opportunity to provide effective smoking cessation interventions.

Method: A toolkit was developed to guide Pre-anesthesia Consultation and Education (PACE) clinic providers when encountering current smokers (CS) or recent smokers (RS). Providers screened patients for smoking history, and when they encountered a current or recent smoker, utilized the algorithm, based on the 5A's framework (ask, advise, assess, assist and arrange) to guide them through the appropriate steps and interventions. The Transtheoretical Model (TTM) was incorporated into the

assess component, thereby guiding providers with subsequent interventions (e.g., counselling, educational materials). Smokers in the preparation stage (ready to quit in < 1 month) were further assisted by arranging referral to the Center for Health Promotion (CHP) or California Smoker's Helpline (CSH). Following the encounter, a data collection sheet was completed and submitted to the author. Descriptive statistics were analyzed for patient demographics, CS: cigarettes, CS: pipe, CS: cigar, CS: years of smoking, CS: ready to quit, CS: counselling, CS: education materials, CS: card/brochure, CS: referred to CHP, CS: referred to CSH, CS: receiving treatment, RS: years of smoking, RS: education materials, RS: support given, cancer diagnosis, and cancer risk linked to smoking. At the end of the data collection period, all providers received and completed a seven-question project evaluation questionnaire. The purpose of the questionnaire was to receive feedback and improve the smoke cessation program.

Results: There were a total of 158 current and recent smokers encountered between August 16 and December 14, 2017. Current smokers totaled 134, accounting for 85% of the group. The average age for the group was 53.64 ($SD = 13.29$), and ranged from 21 to 82. The most frequently used tobacco product observed among the current smokers was cigarettes ($n = 128$), followed by cigars ($n = 7$), and pipe ($n = 2$). Current smokers smoked an average of 29.21 years ($SD = 15.51$, $Min = 1.00$, $Max = 73.00$). Out of the 134 current smokers encountered, the majority of them were ready to quit within 30 days ($n = 92$, 68.66%). Most of the current smokers received counselling ($n = 126$, 94.03%) and educational materials ($n = 86$, 64.18%). Fifty of the current smokers (37.31%) who were ready to quit, accepted referral for smoke cessation counselling/treatment. Only thirteen (9.70%) of the current smokers were already

receiving treatment from another provider. Recent smokers (within 12 months) smoked an average of 29.75 years ($SD = 17.13$, Min = 1.00, Max = 62.00). The majority of the recent smokers received encouragement or support and educational materials. For most of the current or recent smokers with a diagnosis of cancer or possible cancer, their cancer risk could be increased by, or linked to smoking ($n = 33$, 71.74%).

Implications: Preoperative smoke cessation counselling and intervention is of importance for a variety of reasons. Only a small percentage of smokers presenting to the PACE clinic received care or treatment for smoke cessation. Many patients are unaware that smoking up to the day of surgery can place them at increased risk of surgical complications. Woody et al. (2008) report that patients often have a desire to, and sometimes expect providers to speak with them about their smoking history, and assist them with smoke cessation interventions. Most of the current smokers were ready to quit within 30 days. This program has enabled providers to feel more comfortable discussing the implications of smoking, advising them to quit, providing education materials, and offering referral services to those at the appropriate stage of readiness. For those patients who presented with a diagnosis of cancer or possible cancer, their cancer risk could be increased by, or linked to smoking in most cases. Therefore, from a counselling standpoint, greater emphasis may need to be placed on cancer risk and its link to smoking. This hospital, along with many others are adopting Enhanced Recovery After Surgery protocols which include preoperative smoke cessation as one of the core components. Incorporation of these protocols have resulted in significant improvements to include decreased postoperative complications and length of stay. The preoperative period is an excellent time to “seize the moment” and discuss smoke cessation before

surgery. Some may require only minimal intervention, while others may require more intensive intervention. In any case, we as providers have a unique opportunity to intervene, in an effort to minimize the impact of smoking in the perioperative setting, and ultimately improve health outcomes.

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INTRODUCTION

In the preoperative setting, providers will inevitably encounter patients with a smoking history. In the United States, an estimated 8 to 10 million surgical procedures requiring anesthesia are performed on cigarette smokers annually (Mills et al., 2011). It has been well documented that cigarette smoking has negative health implications (e.g., increased risk of surgical complications) for surgical patients. Specifically, active smokers can be at increased risk of perioperative cardiovascular, pulmonary, and wound healing complications, which in turn can result in sequelae such as wound dehiscence, reintubation, repeat surgery, and increased length of stay (Khullar & Maa, 2012). Because these sequelae may have a financial impact on health care as well as negatively impact patient quality of life, determining and using care strategies that may diminish smoking impact in patients seen preoperatively is important.

Smoking cessation prior to any surgery reduces complications (Mills et al., 2011). Longer periods of cessation prior to surgery have resulted in a significant reduction in postoperative complications (Mills et al., 2011). However, information on the effects of smoking and the benefits of smoking cessation on surgical outcomes are not regularly provided to patients in preoperative settings (Khullar & Maa, 2012; Lauerma, 2008). Furthermore, nearly half of surgeons do not regularly provide information or suggest interventions to patients about smoking or tobacco cessation prior to surgery (Khullar & Maa, 2012). Approximately 7 out of 10 cigarette smokers want to quit (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2015). Therefore, the preoperative setting presents an excellent opportunity to introduce and provide effective smoking cessation interventions.

Pathophysiology/Epidemiology of Smoking and Tobacco Cessation

Among the many chemicals in cigarettes, four (nicotine, carbon monoxide, hydrogen cyanide and nitric oxide) are most harmful and contribute to surgical complications (Gourgiotis et al., 2011; Yousefzadeh, Chung, Wong, Warner, & Wong, 2016). Among other things, these toxins work together to negatively affect tissue perfusion, oxygenation, and wound healing (Yousefzadeh et al., 2016). Nicotine, which increases sympathetic activity and carbon monoxide which displaces oxygen on hemoglobin, can elevate blood pressure and heart rate (Gourgiotis et al., 2011; Yousefzadeh et al., 2016). Nicotine also causes vasoconstriction. Smoking itself damages the mucus transport mechanism within the airways resulting in impaired mucus transport, airway hyperactivity, and susceptibility to infection or pneumonia (Yousefzadeh et al., 2016).

Smoking increases the risk of developing a variety of cancers to include lung, head and neck, esophageal, stomach, colon, liver, breast, bladder, kidney, pancreatic, cervical, ovarian, and leukemia (Berg et al., 2013; Ramaswamy, Toll, Chagpar, & Judson, 2016). Smoking also increases the risk of diseases such as coronary artery disease, cerebral vascular disease, peripheral vascular disease, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (Khullar & Maa, 2012; Siu, 2015). Smokers with these conditions may appreciate some reversal of the pathological effects of smoking by quitting prior to surgery.

Other physiologic and psychologic factors have been associated with smoking and the success of smoke cessation. Studies have revealed that women are less motivated and confident to quit, and harbor fears of weight gain following cessation (Minian, Penner,

Voci, & Selby, 2016) . In a randomized controlled trial, Azodi et al. (2009) reported that obesity and low nicotine dependence among those attempting to quit smoking appeared to predict long-term abstinence. In a meta-analysis which looked at genetic variants in the $\alpha 5$ nicotinic cholinergic receptor subunit gene (CHRNA5) on chromosome 15q25, Chen et al. (2015) found that the CHRNA5 variant rs16969968 predicts delayed smoking cessation and the development of lung cancer at earlier ages. Finally, cigarette smoking has been regarded as a means of managing stress; however, studies have shown that patients who abstain from smoking in preparation for surgery do not experience undue cravings or stress (Warner et al., 2008).

Supporting Framework

The framework for this project was supported using two models: The i-PARIHS model, which assisted in planning implementation of a practice change related to tobacco cessation in the pre-operative setting, and Prochaska and DiClemente's transtheoretical (stages of change) model, which was useful for developing protocols/resources for patients.

The PARIHS framework, first published in 1998 and later revised to become the integrated or i-PARIHS framework, is used to successfully implement new knowledge into practice. It consists of core constructs which include facilitation, innovation, recipients, and context (Kitson & Harvey, 2016). Figure 1 provides an overview of the i-PARIHS model and the duties of the facilitator.

The facilitator's role involves developing a plan of action which will ultimately encourage providers or "recipients" to adopt the practice change. Relative to this project, this entailed providing quality evidence to support the benefits of smoke cessation

intervention, in an attempt to decrease peri-operative complications. The plan of action is the focus of the innovation construct. Harvey and Kitzen (2016) reported that providers rarely take evidence from research (e.g., systemic review) and apply it directly into an implementation project. It is therefore necessary to adapt evidence, making it presentable, practical, and applicable to the practice setting. In the preoperative setting, this included compiling evidence about perioperative benefits of smoke cessation, and then presenting it orally and in written form to the providers or “recipients.” Follow-up is also necessary to ensure that team motivation is maintained and behavior change is occurring relative to the new knowledge (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). Context consists of inner (e.g., organizational, local) and outer (e.g., interorganizational) layers.

Facilitator Focus and Activity

What the Facilitator Looks at
What the Facilitator Does

Figure 1. The Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services (i-PARIHS) model (Harvey & Kitson, 2016).

Given that the components of this construct can affect the success of the implementation process, it is important to be aware of such things as leadership support, organizational priorities, and culture (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). Implementation of this project involved making changes to the electronic medical record, in order to gather and document smoking habits/history in more detail. Furthermore, the project involved setting up a referral process, which was ultimately performed electronically. Making these changes required the support of local and organizational leadership which included the Information Technology Department. The extant culture of the organization centers on healthy living; hence, efforts to promote smoke cessation was looked upon favorably.

Prochaska and DiClemente's Transtheoretical Model (Figure 2) provides an understanding of the way a behavior change occurs by describing how people progress through stages of readiness. The stages are identified as: precontemplation, contemplation, preparation, action and maintenance (Prochaska & Velicer, 1997).

Figure 2. Stages of change (Prochaska & Velicer, 1997).

During precontemplation, people are likely unaware, not interested, or unwilling to take action within the next six months (American Society on Aging and American

Society of Consultant Pharmacists Foundation, 2012). Individuals at this stage are not ready for health promotion programs. Contemplation is a stage in which people are planning to take action or make a change within the next 6 months. They are also not ready for health promotion programs. At the preparation stage, people have decided and intend to take action or make a change within the next month. These individuals should be recruited for health promotion programs (Prochaska & Velicer, 1997). Action is a stage in which people have taken action or changed their behavior within the past six months. Finally, during the maintenance stage, people work to maintain the behavior change. The longer individuals remain in this stage, the greater the likelihood of preventing relapse.

In the preoperative setting, it is important for providers to identify the patients' readiness for (stage of) change, and match an appropriate intervention with that stage (Communication for Governance & Accountability Program, 2009). Providers need to understand that patients in the precontemplation stage are not ready for change. Counselling can focus on increasing patients' awareness of the risks of smoking prior to surgery, so they can start thinking more about the behavior and hopefully about quitting. Once patients consider quitting, transition to the contemplation stage has occurred (American Society on Aging and American Society of Consultant Pharmacists Foundation, 2012), and patients are thinking about change and evaluating the benefits of versus the barriers to smoking cessation. It has been suggested that more emphasis should be placed on the benefits of not smoking, with the idea that growing knowledge of benefits makes the barriers less significant and can facilitate transition to the next stage (Prochaska & Velicer, 1997). Patients in the preparation stage are ready for change, and

will report that they want to quit smoking. At this point, referral to a smoke cessation program is appropriate. Patients in the action stage make a change in their behavior; they quit smoking. For the action to count, it must be “sufficient to reduce risks for disease.” (Prochaska & Velicer, p. 39). Therefore, cutting back or changing to “light” cigarettes does not count. Counselling can focus on reinforcing the behavior.

Patients in the maintenance stage are working to sustain their behavior and prevent relapse. Counselling can focus on providing encouragement and reinforcement. If relapse occurs (e.g., termination of action or maintenance stages), patients will regress or “recycle” to the earlier stages of precontemplation or contemplation (DiClemente et al., 1991). Once the stage is correctly assessed, counselling appropriate to the stage can continue.

Purpose

The purpose of this Doctorate in Nursing Practice project was to develop and implement an evidence-based pilot program for smoking cessation in the Pre-anesthesia Consultation and Education (PACE) clinic of a large teaching hospital in the Southwestern U.S. The pilot program included:

- A provider toolkit consisting of:
 - A protocol for clinical interventions based on the 5A’s (Ask, Advise, Assess, Assist, and Arrange) and transtheoretical model.
 - A Sample Script for Smoking Cessation
 - An evidence-based information sheet: Pathophysiology and Perioperative Risks of Smoking, Benefits of Quitting
 - A Guide for Smoking Cessation Patient Education Materials
- Modification of the electronic medical record (EMR)
- Set up of a referral process

- Education of providers on smoking cessation, the toolkit, and referral process
- Evaluation of the pilot program

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Evidence Search

A comprehensive literature search was conducted for this quality improvement project. Five electronic databases were searched for articles pertaining to screening for smoking, smoke cessation interventions and smoke cessation before surgery: CINAHL, PsychINFO, Pubmed, Cochran Library, and Google Scholar. The following search terms were used: smoking AND surgical outcomes, smoking AND operation OR surgery, smoking AND pediatric surgery, smoke cessation OR tobacco cessation AND surgery, smoking AND perioperative OR preoperative AND outcomes, smoke cessation AND interventions, transtheoretical AND smoke cessation, smoke cessation AND theoretical model OR stages of change, smoke cessation AND stages of change, smoke cessation and transtheoretical, smoke cessation AND transtheoretical model AND perioperative, smoke cessation AND educational methods, smoking cessation toolkit. Reference lists were also reviewed for key articles that provided additional pertinent evidence. Searches were limited to peer reviewed articles, and those published in the English language from January 2007 through March 2017 (except for seminal work) involving adults and adolescents. The types of evidence were randomized controlled trials, systematic reviews, meta analyses and guidelines. Excluded from the search were publications that focused on the disease-specific effects of smoking (e.g., HIV, depression) or discussed other behaviors/risk factors that increase perioperative risk for complications (e.g., alcohol use, recreational drug use, obesity, poor nutritional status, physical fitness). Details of the search are described in Tables 1 through 8. The search culminated with 43 articles (and one seminal work) which were ultimately used for this review.

Table 1

Smoke Cessation Using CINAHL

Database	Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
CINAHL	Smoking AND surgical outcomes	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	36	22	14	2
	Smoking AND operation OR surgery	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	1833	1802	31	3
	Smoking AND pediatric surgery	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	2	0	2	0
	Smoking cessation OR tobacco cessation AND surgery	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	149	123	26	3
	Smoking AND perioperative OR preoperative AND outcomes	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	190	163	27	5
	Smoke cessation AND interventions	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	3	1	2	2
	Smoke cessation AND educational methods	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	0	0	0	0
	Smoking cessation toolkit	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	0	0	0	0

Table 2

Stages of Change Using CINAHL

Database	Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
CINAHL	Transtheoretical AND smoke cessation	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	261	242	19	2
	Smoke cessation AND theoretical model OR stages of change	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	594	553	41	2
	Smoke cessation AND stages of change	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	0	0	0	0
	Smoke cessation AND transtheoretical model	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	117	99	18	3
	Smoke cessation AND transtheoretical AND perioperative	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	0	0	0	0

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic. Duplicates were also omitted.

Table 3

Smoke Cessation Using PsychINFO

Database	Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
PsychINFO	Smoking AND surgical outcomes	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	3	0	3	1
	Smoking AND operation OR surgery	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	586	586	0	0
	Smoking AND pediatric surgery	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	6	6	0	0
	Smoking cessation OR tobacco cessation AND surgery	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	20	19	1	0
	Smoking AND perioperative OR preoperative AND outcomes	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	17	17	0	0
	Smoke cessation AND interventions	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	3	2	1	1
	Smoke cessation AND educational methods	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	0	0	0	0
	Smoking cessation toolkit	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	0	0	0	0

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic. Duplicates were also omitted.

Table 4

Stages of Change Using PsycheINFO

Database	Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
PsychINFO	Transtheoretical AND smoke cessation	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	0	0	0	0
	Smoke cessation AND theoretical model OR stages of change	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	106	105	1	0
	Smoke cessation AND stages of change	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	0	0	0	0
	Smoke cessation AND transtheoretical model	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	0	0	0	0
	Smoke cessation AND transtheoretical AND perioperative	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	0	0	0	0

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic. Duplicates were also omitted.

Table 5

Smoke Cessation Using Pubmed

Database	Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Pubmed	Smoking AND surgical outcomes	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	320	303	17	7
	Smoking AND operation OR surgery	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	1868	1833	35	2
	Smoking AND pediatric surgery	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	0	0	0	0
	Smoking cessation OR tobacco cessation AND surgery	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	15	13	2	2
	Smoking AND perioperative OR preoperative AND outcomes	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	445	437	8	2
	Smoke cessation AND interventions	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	9	7	2	2
	Smoke cessation AND educational methods	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	652	646	6	2
	Smoking cessation toolkit	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	20	19	1	0

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic. Duplicates were also omitted.

Table 6

Stages of Change Using Pubmed

Database	Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Pubmed	Transtheoretical AND smoke cessation	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	20	18	2	1
	Smoke cessation AND theoretical model OR stages of change	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	300	299	1	0
	Smoke cessation AND stages of change	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	9	9	0	0
	Smoke cessation AND transtheoretical model	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	0	0	0	0
	Smoke cessation AND transtheoretical AND perioperative	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	0	0	0	0

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic. Duplicates were also omitted.

Table 7

Smoke Cessation Using Cochrane Library

Database	Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Cochrane Library	Smoking AND surgical outcomes	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	8	6	2	0
	Smoking AND operation OR surgery	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	20	17	3	0
	Smoking AND pediatric surgery	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	0	0	0	0
	Smoking cessation OR tobacco cessation AND surgery	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	85	84	1	0
	Smoking AND perioperative OR preoperative AND outcomes	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	73	73	0	0
	Smoke cessation AND interventions	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	70	69	1	1
	Smoke cessation AND educational methods	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	0	0	0	0
	Smoking cessation toolkit	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	5	4	1	0

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic. Duplicates were also omitted.

Table 8

Stages of Change Using Cochrane Library

Database	Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Cochrane Library	Transtheoretical AND smoke cessation	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	77	76	1	1
	Smoke cessation AND theoretical model OR stages of change	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	2	2	0	0
	Smoke cessation AND stages of change	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	5	5	0	0
	Smoke cessation AND transtheoretical model	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	2	2	0	0
	Smoke cessation AND transtheoretical AND perioperative	Peer reviewed, English language, Publish date: 2007 - 2017	0	0	0	0

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic. Duplicates were also omitted.

Screening and Assistance for Smokers

Cigarette smokers who receive some form of assistance with smoke cessation are more likely to quit (Malucky, 2010). However, it is common for providers taxed with busy clinic schedules to forgo screening for cigarette smokers. Despite an estimated 45.3 million smokers in the U.S., less than half received any kind of smoke cessation assistance from health care providers (Malucky, 2010; Park et al., 2015). Screening for smokers aged 11 to 21 years did not increase between 2004 and 2010; furthermore only

19.8% of those smokers received any assistance to quit (Jamal, Dube, Babb, & Malarcher, 2014).

Healthy People 2020 objectives include taking steps to increase quit attempts for adolescents as well as increasing screening and smoke cessation efforts for adults in the outpatient setting (Jamal et al., 2014). It is often reported that patients want, and in some cases, expect health care providers to discuss their smoking history and assist them as appropriate with smoke cessation interventions (Woody, DeCristofaro, & Carlton, 2008). As many as 70% of smokers have an interest in quitting and few (3 to 10%) can do so on their own (Malucky, 2010; Stack & Zillich, 2007). A 2001 - 2002 Centers for Disease Control report indicated that 62% of teens 14 to 18 years of age had a desire to quit and more than 50% of them made at least one quit attempt in the previous year (Robinson & Vail, 2012). With this said, health care providers need to be proactive with interventions for cigarette smokers to assist them toward abstinence.

Theories behind Cessation Strategies

Practice guidelines and models have been developed and used to guide providers and assist smokers toward cessation. If a smoker is unwilling to quit, a recommendation in the 2008 Clinical Practice Guidelines for Treating Tobacco Use and Dependence is use of five “R’s” to motivate a smoker towards cessation (Malucky, 2010). Specific strategies follow:

- Ask the smoker to look at ways in which smoke cessation is *relevant* and could improve his or her life.
- Discuss the *risks* associated with smoking and *rewards* of cessation.
- *Roadblocks* to include withdrawal, relapse and weight gain are common and should be discussed.

- Motivational intervention should be *repetitious*, that is, it should be discussed at every clinic visit (Malucky, 2010).

The 5A's framework is also helpful to assist the provider with brief interventions when engaging cigarette smokers. The US Public Health Service (USPHS) recommends that health care providers screen for tobacco users and manage them accordingly by way of the 5A's framework (*ask* about smoking, *advise* to stop, *assess* readiness to quit, *assist* with a plan, *arrange* follow-up) (Heath, 2017; Park et al., 2015; Siu, 2015; Warner et al., 2011). There is evidence supporting the effectiveness of smoke cessation counselling using the 5A's (Ragucci & Shrader, 2009). Some clinicians have utilized a shorter version of this framework perhaps because of limitations in knowledge on smoke cessation management or time constraints due to heavy patient load. This has included using *ask* and *advise*, then moving forward with referral or "connect" to a quitline. (Yousefzadeh et al., 2016). In an important case control study involving 3336 participants, Park et al. (2015) reported that rates of cessation were not significantly impacted by *ask*, *advise*, and *assess* alone. It was only when *assist* and *arrange* were done, that patient reported abstinence significantly increased. Adding these components can also build rapport with the patient by showing provider concern, and includes providing links and resources which can result in greater success in quitting and increased patient satisfaction with the encounter (Park et al., 2015). Siu (2015) described interventions for smoke cessation which include the 5A's and components of effective counselling interventions. Counselling interventions work to help smokers recognize situations that will increase their likelihood of smoking, find ways to face and overcome barriers to smoke cessation, and work toward a plan to quit. Information about smoking and cessation are also provided, and referrals are offered (Siu, 2015).

Prochaska and his associates developed the transtheoretical model (TTM) to assist cigarette smokers on a path to abstinence (Prochaska & Velicer, 1997). When providers utilize the 5A's framework, the *assess* component is further enhanced by incorporating the TTM (stages of change) into it, hence, guiding the health care provider with subsequent interventions (Woody et al., 2008). It is crucial that the provider determine the stage of readiness to provide the appropriate interventions. The model identifies five levels of readiness: *precontemplation* in which the patient has no plans to quit smoking in the near future; *contemplation* in which the patient has intentions to quit within the next six months; *preparation* in which the patient plans to quit, usually in the next month; *action* in which the patient has quit within the past six months; and *maintenance* in which the patient has abstained from smoking for more than six months (Prochaska & Velicer, 1997). When it is determined that the patient is at the preparation stage, the health care provider can move forward with smoke cessation assistance or referral (e.g., individual/group program or quitline). It is common for patients to relapse one or more times, hence regressing back to precontemplation or contemplation stages. Robinson and Vail (2012) found that the TTM can be of benefit when used for adolescent smokers to change smoking behavior and direct them towards smoke cessation. Several studies that looked at ways to help adolescents quit smoking found that considering the person's readiness for change (preparation), supporting that behavior change, and increasing motivation were beneficial (Stanton & Grimshaw, 2013).

Combination Strategies for Smoking Cessation

Given that smoking is a learned behavior as well as a physical addiction, several studies have indicated that quit rates are greatly improved, and in some cases, nearly

doubled when a combination of counselling and pharmacologic therapy are used (Park et al., 2015; Woody et al., 2008; Yousefzadeh et al., 2016). Nicotine dependency can adversely affect the success of smoking cessation, hence nicotine replacement therapy (NRT) is an effective way to manage the effects of nicotine abstinence (Azodi et al., 2009; Eslami et al., 2012; Newhall et al., 2017). Medications commonly used for adult patients include NRT, bupropion, and varenicline. However, NRT, bupropion, and varenicline have not been found to be of benefit for adolescent smokers (Patnode et al., 2013; Stanton & Grimshaw, 2013). The U.S Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF) has no recommendation for the use of NRT, bupropion, or varenicline in pregnant women over 18 years of age, due to lack of, or no evidence on the benefit of these therapies (Siu, 2015). NRT may be less effective for women when compared to men—perhaps because women tend to obtain satisfaction from smoking with non-nicotine factors such as the sight and smell of smoke (Minian et al., 2016). The USPSFT reports that there is insufficient evidence to support the use of electronic nicotine delivery systems (ENDS) to assist in smoke cessation, therefore there are no recommendations available at this time (Siu, 2015). The American Congress of Obstetricians and Gynecologists and the American Heart Association do recommend however, that ENDS use be included as part of patients' tobacco use assessment in the medical record (Siu, 2015).

Timing/Intensity of Cessation Strategies

Smoke cessation interventions provided preoperatively not only provide short term benefits, but also enable patients to work toward long term smoke cessation. Short term benefits include an immediate reduction in carboxyhemoglobin and nicotine levels in the blood stream (Lauerma, 2008). Brief interventions less than 4 weeks prior to

surgery contribute to smoke cessation, but do not have a significant effect on reducing postoperative complications (Mills et al., 2011; Myers, Hajek, Hinds, & McRobbie, 2011). Intensive interventions or counselling (≥ 20 minutes plus > 1 follow up visit) that include pharmacotherapy at least 3 weeks prior to surgery have resulted in decreased postoperative complications as well as increased success with long term smoke cessation (Azodi et al., 2009; Thomsen, Tønnesen, & Møller, 2009; Thomsen, Villebro, & Møller, 2014; Wong, Lam, Abrishami, Chan, & Chung, 2012). No significant differences were found in terms of effectiveness and long-term cessation success in one study comparing brief interventions with more intensive interventions in preoperative clinics (Yousefzadeh et al., 2016). Zaki, Abrishami, Wong and Chung (2008) found that interventions in a preoperative clinic (e.g., counselling, pharmacotherapy, brochures) resulted in a significantly higher cessation rate at three and six months follow up when compared to those who received usual care (brief advice only).

The USPSTF found substantial evidence that counselling (one on one, quitlines, self-help materials) alone or with pharmacotherapy had a significant positive impact on smoke cessation (Siu, 2015). This was evident in a recent study by Newhall et al. (2017) which found that patients who received brief counselling, were offered smoke cessation medications, and referred to quitlines were much more interested in quitting than those who received usual care (minimal smoke cessation counselling only). Similar outcomes were appreciated when pharmacotherapy was used with or without counselling (Siu, 2015). The ideal intensity of preoperative smoke cessation intervention is still not known (Thomsen et al., 2014).

In a systematic review and meta-analysis, Mills et al. (2011) reported that longer periods of cessation prior to surgery results in significantly reduced postoperative complications with the magnitude of effect increasing by 19% for each week of cessation prior to surgery. In a subsequent systematic review and meta-analysis, Wong, Lam, Abrishami, Chan and Chung (2012) showed that postoperative respiratory complications can be reduced with at least four weeks of smoke cessation prior to surgery, and three to four weeks of smoke cessation to appreciate a decrease in wound-healing complications. Finally, there is no evidence to suggest that quitting a few weeks or less before surgery will result in perioperative complications (Myers et al., 2011).

Implementing Smoke Cessation Strategies

In the perioperative arena, many anesthesiologists and surgeons may ask patients about smoking, but few advise them to quit or provide smoke cessation interventions due to a lack of time or knowledge regarding counselling or smoke cessation medications (Newhall et al., 2017; Yousefzadeh et al., 2016). Other reasons for failure to advise/counsel include inadequate or no reimbursement and lack of institutional support (Jamal et al., 2014). Others believe that the perioperative period is an opportune time or “teachable moment” for smoke cessation (Glasgow et al., 2009; Newhall et al., 2017; Shi & Warner, 2010). Hence, providers in the preoperative clinic have a unique opportunity to identify smokers and provide smoke cessation interventions.

It is important to understand the value of the “teachable moment.” Surgery is a significant life event, and many smokers are unaware that smoke cessation can decrease postoperative complications. Therefore, this life event can serve as a significant motivator to quit smoking prior to surgery, engage in smoke cessation practices and

services, and impact long-term health (Warner et al., 2008). Brief interventions, those less than 10 minutes (e.g., counselling, self-help materials, pharmacotherapy, quitlines), can significantly increase motivation to quit and smoke cessation outcomes (Malucky, 2010; Siu, 2015). In a study by Bottorff, Seaton, & Lamont (2015), only half of patients surveyed had knowledge that smoking up to the day of surgery could place them at increased risk for surgical complications. Smokers who understand the risks of smoking are more likely to quit and maintain longer periods of cessation (Newhall et al., 2017). There are factors such as low socioeconomic status, and living with a smoking partner which can hamper a smoker's success towards abstinence (Azodi et al., 2009). Low socioeconomic status is associated with lower levels of education and health literacy; therefore these smokers may be less receptive to health promoting or smoke cessation interventions (Harwood, Salsberry, Ferketich, & Wewers, 2007).

Counselling should focus on the benefits of quitting and include information on perioperative risks. This in turn can transition patients through the stages of change. When patients consider a behavior change, the costs and benefits of the behavior are considered. Behavior change can be anticipated once the benefits outweigh the costs (Eslami et al., 2012). If the stage of readiness is preparation, and a quit date is set, steps toward appropriate counselling resources or quitlines can commence.

During the intervention process, Yousefzadeh et al. (2016) has shown that connecting patients with counselling services by way of electronic referrals within patients' health records increased their enrollment 13-fold. This approach facilitates patients into more intensive counselling and pharmacotherapy, as such decreasing postoperative complications and positively impacting long term smoke cessation.

Increased intensity in terms of counselling has been shown to have increased benefit with respect to short and long-term cessation rates (Siu, 2015). In a study conducted by Warner et al. (2011), high satisfaction with quitlines was found, with 87.1% of users rating them as excellent or very good. Quitline participants found it to be helpful for smoke cessation, and would recommend quitlines to others (Warner et al., 2011).

Quitlines are a convenient means by which smokers can receive counselling (versus face to face counselling) and free NRT (Yousefzadeh et al., 2016). Telephone counselling initiated by providers or recruiters increased rates of smoke cessation at six or more months (Siu, 2015; Warner et al., 2008). It is important to motivate the smoker to move forward with quitline services (Warner et al., 2011). This can be done by talking with them about these services and providing written information such as a brochure. Finally, another method that has shown promise is the use of text messaging to provide smoke cessation interventions. Riley, Obermayer, & Jean-Mary (2008) evaluated text messaging interventions based on the TTM among college smokers, and found them to be not only well accepted, but resulting in a 42% abstinence rate six weeks after the program was initiated.

Cost Savings

Any costs associated with organizing or maintaining smoke cessation interventions within the preoperative clinic or within the organization would certainly be recovered by savings associated with reduced postoperative complications and of course, long term sequelae of smoking (Jamal et al., 2014; Yousefzadeh et al., 2016). Enhanced Recovery After Surgery (ERAS) protocols adopted by many hospitals around the world include preoperative smoke cessation as one of the core components, and have resulted in

significant improvements not only in clinical outcomes (i.e., decreased postoperative complications and length of stay) but in cost savings (Ljungqvist, Scott, & Fearon, 2017).

Summary

In conclusion, smokers who receive some form of assistance in the outpatient pre-surgery setting are more likely to quit. Therefore, to meet the objectives of *Healthy People 2020*, and well as play a role in ERAS, it would be prudent to implement smoke cessation interventions in the preoperative setting. Brief interventions have been shown to be of benefit, and the 5A's framework can be used effectively to guide providers when encountering smokers. The framework is further enhanced by incorporating into it the TTM, which will guide the provider with subsequent interventions. To ensure that the providers can and will perform these interventions and effectively assist smokers on a path to smoke cessation, they will require education and training. While short term interventions (provided less than four weeks prior to surgery) certainly have benefits, initiating interventions at least three to four weeks prior to surgery have been shown to have an impact on decreasing postoperative complications. Effective interventions typically include counselling, pharmacotherapy, quitlines and brochures. Counselling should focus on benefits of quitting and perioperative risks. Quitlines have been shown to be effective, and highly rated by smokers. Smoke cessation has been shown to improve significantly with the addition of pharmacotherapy in non-pregnant adults; however, it has not been shown to be of benefit for adolescent smokers. Finally, more intensive interventions decrease postoperative complications and increase success of short and long-term smoke cessation. Therefore, effective smoke cessation interventions

for preoperative patients should include assistance with referral for intensive interventions, provided the smoker is at the appropriate stage of readiness.

METHODS

The purpose of this project was to develop and introduce an evidence-based pilot program for smoking cessation in the Pre-anesthesia Consultation and Education (PACE) clinic of a large teaching hospital in the U.S. The program included:

- A provider toolkit consisting of:
 - A protocol for clinical interventions based on the 5A's and TTM
 - A Sample Script for Smoking Cessation
 - An evidence-based information sheet: Pathophysiology and Perioperative Risks of Smoking, Benefits of Quitting
 - A Guide for Smoking Cessation Patient Education Materials
- Modification of the electronic medical record (EMR)
- Set up of a referral process
- Education of providers on smoking cessation, the toolkit, referral process, and data collection.
- Evaluation of the pilot program

Sample/Setting

The project occurred at the PACE clinic of a large teaching hospital in the Southwestern U.S. The target or recipients for the improvement were the nurse practitioners and rotating anesthesia residents at the clinic (who utilized the toolkit for patients), and the surgical patients who were smokers presenting to the clinic.

Ethical Considerations

A student project application was submitted to the manager of academic relations, Department of Staff Development. On March 6, 2017, clearance was obtained to begin the project at the organization (Appendix A). As this was a quality improvement project, Human Subjects' Protection (IRB) was considered, and was not necessary.

Preliminary Work

During initial meetings with clinic staff and an expert provider at the Center for Health Promotion, information was gained about the smoke cessation service currently available, types of insurance accepted, and the referral process in place. Patients meet one-on-one with providers who specialize in addiction medicine. Pharmacologic therapies are provided as needed. Meetings or appointments are set up in intervals (e.g., initial, two weeks, four weeks, three months, six months, and twelve months), and after one year, if there is an urge to restart smoking, additional visits are scheduled. The Center for Health Promotion is contracted with many of the major insurance companies, and still others will cover smoke cessation, however, those with the Inland Empire Health Plan (IEHP) require prior authorization. An electronic referral process is utilized by other services within this healthcare organization. Discussions also took place with a professor of preventative care at the School of Public Health to gain similar information on their smoke cessation program. The program (Breathe Free 2), based on a four-week series of classes, does not offer pharmacologic therapies, and is available only to employees and their spouses. The Center for Health Promotion was therefore chosen as a referral site for this project.

Electronic requests or tickets were submitted to information technology (IT) to modify the electronic medical record/tobacco assessment section that was in use at the PACE clinic. These changes enabled PACE providers to collect additional information (i.e., select the types of tobacco and smokeless tobacco used), hence, standardizing the data collected between anesthesiologists, nurse anesthetists, and nurse practitioners. An additional field was requested to include electronic nicotine delivery systems (ENDS)

use. Unfortunately, this method of nicotine use is currently not available to include in the tobacco assessment section, therefore, the addition of an ENDS field has been submitted to Epic as an enhancement request. In the meantime, usage of ENDS is documented in the comments field.

A search was conducted on the hospital's "VIP" or home page for information or resources related to cigarette smoking or smoke cessation. A variety of smoke cessation websites were obtained as well as articles and publications on smoking, smoke cessation and ENDS. Additionally, contact information on the Living Whole BREATHE program for employees offered by the School of Public Health was found, as well as referral forms for the Center for Health promotion and Family Medicine. A search was also conducted (using the *Clinical References & Patient Instructions* tab) for any patient education materials related to smoking or smoke cessation available as an attachment for the after-visit summary. Several attachments were found which included: Benefits of Living Smoke Free, Why Do You Smoke, Smoking Cessation, Tips for Quitting Smoking, Getting Support for Quitting Smoking, Planning to Quit Smoking, Staying Smoke Free, and Coping with Smoking Withdrawal.

Procedures

The Toolkit

This was an evidence-based quality improvement project. It involved the development of a protocol/algorithm for clinical interventions based on the 5A's framework (ask, advise, assess, assist and arrange). The *assess* component was augmented by incorporating the TTM (stages of change) into it, thereby, guiding providers with subsequent interventions (Appendix B). *A Sample Script for Smoking*

Cessation was developed using the 5A's framework together with information from the Pathophysiology/Epidemiology of Smoking and Tobacco Cessation, and Review of Literature sections. It is available as a guide for providers when discussing smoking history and cessation (Appendix C). The *Pathophysiology and Perioperative Risks of Smoking/Benefits of Quitting* is an evidenced based information sheet designed to guide providers with patient education and counselling. It was also compiled using information from the Pathophysiology/Epidemiology of Smoking and Tobacco Cessation, and Review of Literature sections (Appendix D). Educational materials found in the *Clinical References & Patient Instructions* tab (Benefits of Living Smoke Free, Why Do You Smoke, Smoking Cessation, Getting Support for Quitting Smoking, Planning to Quit Smoking, Staying Smoke Free, Coping with Smoking Withdrawal) are attached to the after-visit summary, and the provider is assisted in selecting these materials by referring to the *Guide for Smoking Cessation Patient Education Materials* (Appendix E).

California Smokers' Helpline brochures for the adult or teen smoker are also provided as needed. The brochures entitled, *Want to Quit Smoking* (English/Spanish), and *Want to Help a Teen Quit Smoking*, were ordered from the California Smoker's Helpline and received at the PACE clinic on July 31, 2017. The toolkit was designed to guide the PACE provider (recipient) through the smoke cessation assessment and management process. It was initially available on paper, and once reviewed and approved by the interdisciplinary team, electronic requests or tickets were submitted to the information technology department. Subsequently, the toolkit was built onto the PACE website. Additional work with the information technology department made it possible to

establish links, thus enabling PACE providers to refer patients to the Center for Health Promotion and the California Smoker's Helpline.

Project Implementation

On July 13, 2017, the project was presented to the interdisciplinary team, consisting of representatives from the departments of anesthesia, nurse anesthesia, perioperative services, PACE, and the Director of Nursing Research. The presentation was well received, and the project was approved for implementation.

Before the project began, PACE clinic staff or "recipients" received education and training. The presentation on smoking cessation, the toolkit, referral processes and data collection took place on August 16, 2017. In coordination with the Perioperative Services Clinical Educator, a continuing education (CE) application was completed and lecture materials were submitted to the Nursing Staff Development Department for review; hence, all participants received CE credit. The project is now part of the new provider orientation which includes the monthly rotation of incoming residents.

The Practice Change

Prior to the implementation of this project on August 16, 2017, patients at the PACE clinic only received screening for tobacco use. The practice change that was envisioned reflects several provider behaviors. Currently, providers screen patients for smoking history; this information is entered into the patient's medical record using the tobacco assessment section (revised May 8, 2017). If patients are current or recent smokers, providers then use the smoke cessation algorithm to guide them through the appropriate steps and interventions. A laminated copy of the algorithm is posted in all the patient rooms for immediate access (*The Guide for Smoking Cessation Patient*

Education Materials is on the back side). Current smokers are advised to quit, and then assessed for stage of readiness. Those in the precontemplation, contemplation or preparation stages receive counselling with emphasis on perioperative risks of smoking and the benefits of quitting. Appropriate educational materials are provided/attached to the after-visit summary, and may include a California Smokers' Helpline brochure. Smokers in the preparation stage are further assisted by offering and arranging referral to the Center for Health Promotion or the California Smokers' Helpline. Recent smokers (e.g., action or maintenance stage) receive encouragement or support and educational materials if needed. No action is needed for those who have quit ≥ 5 years ago.

Data Collection

On the day of project implementation, data collection sheets (Appendix C) were placed in all of the patient rooms. When a provider encountered a current smoker (CS) or recent smoker (RS), the data collection sheet was completed and submitted to the author for data entry. Data collection consisted of demographic information, diagnosis, and smoking status (current smoker or recent smoker). Patient demographics collected were age, sex and ethnicity. Data collected for current smokers were: tobacco product smoked (cigarettes, pipe, cigar), number of years smoking, ready to quit within one month, counselling provided, educational materials provided, card/brochure provided, referral to Center for Health Promotion (CHP)/California Smoker's Helpline (CSH), and currently receiving care/treatment. Data collected for recent smokers were: number of years of smoking, encouragement or support given, and educational materials provided (Appendix F).

Data Analysis and Project Evaluation

Data analysis was completed using Tableau version 9.3 and Intellectus Statistics online computer software (Intellectus Statistics, 2017). Descriptive statistics were analyzed for patient demographics, CS: cigarettes, CS: pipe, CS: cigar, CS: years of smoking, CS: ready to quit, CS: counselling, CS: education materials, CS: card/brochure, CS: referred to CHP, CS: referred to CSH, CS: receiving treatment, RS: years of smoking, RS: education materials, RS: support given, cancer diagnosis, and cancer risk linked to smoking. At the end of the data collection period, all providers received and completed a seven-question project evaluation questionnaire. The purpose of the questionnaire was to receive feedback and improve the smoke cessation program (Appendix G).

RESULTS

Data Collection

There were a total of 158 current and recent smokers encountered between August 16 and December 14, 2017. Current smokers totaled 134, accounting for 85% of the group. Recent smokers totaled 24, accounting for 15% of the group. The average age in years for the group was 53.64 ($SD = 13.29$), and ranged from 21 to 82. There were 71 (45%) males and 87 (55%) females. The most frequently observed category of ethnicity was white ($n = 106, 67%$). Frequencies and percentages are presented in Table 9.

Table 9

Ethnicity of Sample

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Ethnicity		
Asian	2	1.27
Black	19	12.03
Hispanic	25	15.82
MiddleEast	2	1.27
Other/Multiple	4	2.53
White	106	67.09
Missing	0	0.00

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

The most frequently used tobacco product observed among the current smokers was cigarettes ($n = 128$), followed by cigars ($n = 7$), and pipe ($n = 2$). Current smokers had smoked an average of 29.21 years ($SD = 15.51$, $Min = 1.00$, $Max = 73.00$). Figure 3 provides a comparison between current cigarette smokers, cigar smokers, and pipe smokers.

Figure 3. Current smokers. Three values represent percentage of smokers, number of smokers, and average years of smoking.

Out of the 134 current smokers encountered, the majority of them were ready to quit within 30 days ($n = 92$, 68.66%). Figure 4 provides a comparison of current smokers who were ready to quit versus those who were not.

Figure 4. Current Smokers: Ready to Quit. Three values represent percentage of smokers, number of smokers, and average years of smoking.

Most of the current smokers received counselling (n = 126, 94.03%) and educational materials (n = 86, 64.18%). Referral cards for the Center for Health Promotion or brochures for the California Smoker's Helpline were provided as needed (n = 28, 20.90%). Fifty of the current smokers (37.31%) who were ready to quit, accepted referral for smoke cessation counselling/treatment. Only thirteen (9.70%) of the current smokers were already receiving treatment from another provider. Table 10 provides the intervention details.

Table 10

Current Smokers: Interventions

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Counselling provided		
Yes	126	94.03
No	8	5.97
Education materials provided		
Yes	86	64.18
No	48	35.82
Card/Brochure provided		
Yes	28	20.90
No	106	79.10
Referred to Center for Health Promotion		
Yes	28	20.90
No	106	79.10
Referred to California Smoker's Helpline		
Yes	22	16.42
No	112	83.58
Currently receiving care/treatment		
Yes	13	9.70
No	121	90.30

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

Recent smokers (within 12 months) smoked an average of 29.75 years ($SD = 17.13$, $Min = 1.00$, $Max = 62.00$). The majority of the recent smokers received encouragement or support and educational materials. Frequencies and percentages are presented in Table 11.

Table 11

Recent Smokers: Interventions

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Encouragement/Support given		
Yes	23	95.83
No	1	4.17
Educational materials provided		
Yes	16	66.67
No	8	33.33

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

Most of the current or recent smokers who presented to the PACE clinic were not having surgery to treat a diagnosis of cancer (Table 12). However, for those who presented with a diagnosis of cancer or possible cancer, their cancer risk could be increased by, or linked to smoking in most of the cases ($n = 33$, 71.74%). Figure 5 compares those with cancer risk linked to smoking versus those with cancer not linked to smoking.

Table 12

Cancer Diagnosis

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Cancer diagnosis		
Yes	27	17.09
No	112	70.89
Possible	19	12.03

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

Figure 5. Cancer risk linked to smoking. Three values represent percentage of smokers, number of smokers, and average years of smoking.

Project Evaluation

Ten project evaluation forms consisting of seven questions were distributed to PACE providers, and eight forms were received and reviewed by the author. All of the providers felt the toolkit was helpful and easy to understand and follow, however, one commented: “it does take a few minutes of your time.” Things they liked about the toolkit were: overall user friendliness, ease of access to referral options “especially with the time constraints for patient visits,” talking with patients about benefits of smoke cessation, and providing referral options. One provider wrote that she liked “seeing the excitement when telling them there are things available to help them in cessation.” When asked about suggestions for improvement to the toolkit, one provider felt it was difficult to print (attached educational materials) to the after-visit summary, and another felt it would be nice to have a referral pop-up window for all smokers. All of the providers thought modifications to the tobacco assessment section were helpful (two stating: “very helpful”); one provider thought the modifications “save time when recording data assessments.” When asked about suggestions for improvement to the tobacco assessment section, one provider reported this section does not open automatically for kids, while another provider would like to see a vaping section added. Thoughts on the referral process resulted in additional responses reporting its user friendliness, while two other providers were curious to know how many patients actually followed through with, or utilized the referrals provided to them. Providers were then asked to offer any thoughts or suggestions regarding the smoke cessation program at PACE. Responses were as follows: “Very comprehensive for those willing to quit;” “A very useful tool for the patients; many patients were very grateful for it;” and “It brings awareness to surgical

patients that smoking can affect the recovery.” Other providers wrote: “This process helped me to focus on this area of our screening.”; and “I hope we continue to utilize these tools for our patients.” Finally, one provider indicated that shared documentation from the history section (location of smoking assessment) to the PACE note would be nice.

DISCUSSION

As providers in the pre-operative clinic, we inevitably encounter cigarette smokers preparing for surgery. As mentioned previously, information on the effects of smoking and benefits of smoke cessation on surgical outcomes are not regularly provided to patients in the preoperative setting (Khullar & Maa, 2012; Lauerman, 2008). Given the negative health implications of smoking for surgical patients, it is imperative that we as providers implement care strategies in an effort to diminish smoking impact on surgical outcomes. As such, development and implementation of a smoking cessation program at the Pre-anesthesia Counselling and Education (PACE) clinic commenced.

There are an estimated 45.3 million smokers in the U.S, and less than half of them receive any kind of smoke cessation assistance from health care providers (Malucky, 2010; Park et al., 2015). This statement is reinforced in this group of smokers which revealed that < 10% of them were currently receiving care or treatment for smoke cessation at the time they presented to the PACE clinic.

The number of cigarette smokers encountered (n = 128) far exceeded the number of cigar and pipe smokers (n = 9), which could be due to the popularity of cigarettes. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2015) report that 7 out of 10 (70%) cigarettes smokers want to quit. In this group, 69% of the current smokers were ready to quit smoking in ≤ 30 days. Of the remaining 31% (those not ready to quit), females outnumbered the males by a ratio of 2:1. This could be explained by studies which have revealed that women are less motivated and confident to quit, and fear weight gain (Minian et al., 2016).

Most of the current smokers received counselling (94%) and educational materials (64%). However, fewer smokers received educational materials because: 1) They did not desire the materials, 2) Providers may have been pressed for time, and chose to forgo the additional steps required to choose and attach the materials to the after-visit summary, and 3) Some difficulty may have been experienced with the process of attaching/printing educational materials. Woody et al. (2008) report that patients often have a desire to, and sometimes expect providers to speak with them about their smoking history, and assist them with smoke cessation interventions. This was apparent on numerous occasions as providers reported patients' interest in these discussions, and were happy to have options to help them with smoke cessation. Additionally, patients were often surprised to learn about the risks of smoking and benefits of quitting in preparation for surgery. Bottorff et al. (2015) found that only half of the patients surveyed had knowledge that smoking up until the day of surgery put them at increased risk of surgical complications.

Yousefzadeh et al. (2016) reported that connecting patients with counselling services by way of electronic referrals within the patient record increased their enrollment by 13-fold. As such, electronic referrals were set up, and used to refer patients to the Center for Health Promotion and California Smoker's Helpline, hence facilitating patients into more intensive counselling and pharmacotherapy. Fifty (37.31%) of the current smokers who were ready to quit were referred for smoke cessation counselling services. Many of the current smokers who were ready to quit did not accept referral, because they felt they could quit on their own. Most of the recent smokers received support or encouragement (96%), and educational materials (67%). Reasons for the

decrease in distribution of educational materials to the recent smokers are similar to those mentioned previously for current smokers.

The association between cigarette smoking and cancer risk is well established. There are a variety of cancers in which smoking has been implicated which go beyond the lung, head and neck (e.g., bladder, breast, cervical, kidney, liver, ovarian). The number of current smokers and recent smokers with a diagnosis of cancer or possible cancer presenting to PACE was small (n = 42, 27%) in comparison to the entire group. However, for most of them with cancer or possible cancer, their cancer risk could be increased by or linked to smoking (n = 33, 72%).

Prior to implementation of this project, patients were only screened for smoking history. It is not uncommon for providers to forgo smoke cessation counselling or interventions due to lack of time or knowledge. However, as a result of this program, providers feel more comfortable discussing the implications of smoking with patients, advising them to quit, and offering referral services to those at the appropriate stage of readiness. As studies have shown, such interventions can significantly increase motivation to quit and positively impact smoke cessation outcomes (Malucky, 2010; Siu, 2015).

Based on the data and provider comments, changes to the program are anticipated. Work will continue with IT to streamline the steps required to choose and attach educational materials to the after-visit summary in an effort reduce the time and labor intensity of this task. Additional work with IT will include: automatic access to the tobacco assessment section for children; follow-up on the enhancement request for the addition of an ENDS use field; and shared documentation from the history section

(location of smoking assessment) to the PACE note. Finally, counselling will include a greater emphasis on cancer risk, and its link to smoking.

Implications for Practice

This quality improvement project has important implications for practice. Preoperative smoke cessation counselling and intervention is of importance for a variety of reasons. In this project, it was determined that only a small percentage of the group presenting to the PACE clinic received care or treatment for smoke cessation. Many patients were unaware that smoking up to the day of surgery can place them at increased risk of surgical complications. Hence, counselling included perioperative risks of smoking and benefits of quitting. This hospital, along with many others are adopting Enhanced Recovery After Surgery (ERAS) protocols which include preoperative smoke cessation as one of the core components. Incorporation of these protocols have resulted in significant improvements to include decreased postoperative complications and length of stay. While the ideal intervention intensity for smoke cessation prior to surgery is still not known, a reduction in postoperative complications can be appreciated when smoke cessation begins as early as three to four weeks prior to surgery (Thomsen et al., 2014; Wong et al., 2012). Additionally, there is no evidence to suggest that quitting any time prior to surgery will result in perioperative complications (Myers et al., 2011). Brief abstinence prior to surgery can result in an immediate reduction in carboxyhemoglobin and nicotine levels in the blood stream which can improve hemodynamics prior to surgery and anesthesia (Lauerman, 2008). The earlier the smoking patient can be seen and receive smoke cessation intervention, the greater the likelihood of appreciating improved perioperative outcomes.

Providers received training prior to the implementation of the smoking cessation project, and as such, feel more comfortable taking part in discussions with patients on the implications of smoking, advising them to quit, and offering referral services. However, from a counselling standpoint, greater emphasis may need to be placed on cancer risk and its link to smoking. Berg et al. (2013) report that patients may not be fully aware of other cancers aside from lung, head and neck that are connected to smoking. Finally, this project (i.e., toolkit) could be utilized in settings outside of preoperative clinics. For example, in primary care settings or surgeons' offices, the toolkit could be used for current or recent smokers preparing for surgery.

Conclusion

Patients have a desire to discuss their smoking history with health care providers. Whether it is a young patient who has just started smoking, or an older patient who has smoked for many years, we as providers can seize the moment and take the opportunity to convince them to quit before surgery. While some smokers may require only minimal intervention, others may require more intensive intervention. In any case, we as providers at the PACE clinic now have a unique opportunity to intervene, in an effort to minimize the impact of smoking in the perioperative setting, and ultimately, improve health outcomes.

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APPENDIX A
TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Table 1

Pathophysiology of Smoking and Smoke Cessation

Author/Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusions/Study Limitations/Appropriateness
Chen et al. (2015) To determine if variation in CHRNA5 affects age of smoking cessation and onset of lung cancer.	Meta-analysis. Associations between age of smoke cessation, age of lung cancer were drawn from ILCOO, GAME-ON Consortia TRICL, DRIVE, Genetic Epidemiology of COPD Study, Collaborative Genetic Study of Nicotine Dependence, 3 studies from dbGap database.	Results from 24 datasets (n = 29,072)	7 studies discovered via disease other than smoking related; 17 studies were smoking related. Inclusion required patients to have smoked in their lifetime.	CHRNA5 variant (rs16969968) associated with delayed smoke cessation (4-year delay in median age (56 years vs 52 years), 95% CI, P = .0042) compared to low risk group. rs16969968 also associated with 4 year earlier median age (61 years vs 65 years) of lung cancer diagnosis (95% CI, P = 1.1×10^{-5})	Supports clinical significance of CHRNA5 variant as genetic marker of nicotine dependence. Smoking cessation & quantity self-reported. Could not test effect of cessation treatment, information not available. Assumed use of medication not common as use in general population not common. Examined 1 variant, however, there are many variants contributing to smoking cessation. Study will be helpful for my project.

Note. CHRNA5 = $\alpha 5$ nicotine cholinergic receptor subunit gene.

Table 2

Screening for Smoking and Smoke Cessation Interventions

Author/Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample/Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusions/Limitations Appropriateness
<p>Heath et al. (2017)</p> <p>Identify relationships between 5A's, individual/organization's attributes of excellence, & intention to integrate smoke cessation interventions.</p>	<p>Descriptive, correlational study design.</p> <p>Variables of interest:</p> <p>Confidence in skills to help patients quit;</p> <p>Value of learning how to integrate effective tobacco-cessation interventions into practice;</p> <p>Intention to start integrating tobacco-cessation interventions into practice.</p>	<p>1773 completed surveys from nurses attending American Association of Critical-Care Nurses National Teaching Institute in Boston, Orlando & Chicago in a 3-year period (2011 - 2013).</p>	<p>Confidence in skills (5A's): Likert scale, 1 = no confidence, 5 = high confidence.</p> <p>Value of learning effective interventions: Likert scale, 1 = no value, 5 = high value.</p> <p>Intentions to integrate 5A's: Likert scale, 1 = no intention, 5 = high intention.</p>	<p>Nurses with standing orders for tobacco dependence 5 times more likely to be highly confident with 5A skills ($p < .001$), 3.4 times more likely to have high intentions to integrate tobacco cessation into practice ($p < .001$).</p>	<p>Health care facilities with standing orders for tobacco-dependence management have nurses with ↑ confidence to help patients quit with effective intervention.</p> <p>Inability to generalize to general nursing population.</p> <p>Unable to control for nurses responding from same hospital/unit.</p> <p>Did not ask about prior knowledge of 5A's</p> <p>Participants interest in smoke cessation?</p> <p>Helpful for project.</p>
<p>Park et al. (2015)</p> <p>To examine:</p> <p>Rates of delivery of the 5A's to participants</p>	<p>Case-control design.</p> <p>IV:</p> <p>Delivery of 5A's by 1 year</p> <p>Assist by 1 year</p>	<p>Participants from 23 American College of Radiology Imaging Network-National Lung Screening Trial sites who were current</p>	<p>5A's:</p> <p>Ask (ask you about smoking),</p> <p>Advise (advise you to stop smoking),</p>	<p>Delivery of 5A's 1 year following screening:</p> <p>Ask, 77.2%; Advise, 75.6%; Assess, 63.4%; Assist,</p>	<p>Results indicate that PCP's who provide assistance to help patients quit smoking (talk about quitting, medication, counseling), and/or arrange follow-up</p>

Author/Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample/Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusions/Limitations Appropriateness
<p>smoking at time of enrollment;</p> <p>Effect of the 5A's on smokers' quitting behavior;</p> <p>Patient factors associated with smoke cessation following delivery of the 5A's.</p>	<p>DV: Smoke cessation</p>	<p>smokers (August 2002 – April 2004).</p> <p>n = 3336</p> <p>1668 cases, 1668 matched controls.</p>	<p>Assess (ask you about interest in quitting),</p> <p>Assist (talk about how to quit, recommend NRT, pharmacotherapy, counseling),</p> <p>Arrange (suggest follow up visit or telephone call).</p> <p>Assist delivery: Physician visits, talk about quitting, medication, counseling.</p>	<p>56.4%; and Arrange follow-up, 10.4%</p> <p>Receipt of the Ask, Advise, Assess not significantly associated with quitting.</p> <p>Assist associated with 40% ↑ odds of quitting.</p> <p>Arrange associated with 46% ↑ in odds of quitting.</p>	<p>can increase smoke cessation.</p> <p>Approximately 50% of smokers reported receiving post screen follow-up in the primary care setting; cessation medications and counseling were not regularly provided.</p> <p>Generalizability limited; patients in context of clinical trial.</p> <p>Helpful for project.</p>
<p>Ragucci et al. (2009)</p> <p>To determine rates of smoking cessation and movement along the TTM as well as use of pharmacotherapy.</p>	<p>Observational study</p> <p>IV: Implementation of a template</p> <p>DV's: Smoke cessation;</p> <p>Movement along TTM;</p> <p>Use of smoke cessation pharmacotherapy.</p>	<p>90 current smokers from 3 clinics at the Medical University of South Carolina between April 2007 and March 2008.</p>	<p>Template: Smoking status, Type of tobacco, amount, duration (years), past quit attempts;</p> <p>Symptoms of nicotine addiction (yes/no);</p> <p>Desire to quit in 30 days (yes/no);</p> <p>Assessment: Precontemplation, Contemplation,</p>	<p>42% achieved smoking cessation postintervention.</p> <p>Movement along TTM; 58% progressing to at least next stage.</p> <p>Several pharmacologic therapies used, most commonly varenicline.</p>	<p>Incorporating smoke cessation template into electronic record together with providing education during pharmacy referral visits effective way to assist patients in progressing toward & achieving smoke cessation.</p> <p>Potential recall bias in terms of smoking history.</p> <p>No biochemical verification.</p>

Author/Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample/Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusions/Limitations Appropriateness
			Preparation Action, Maintenance; Follow up (yes/no)	39% used no medications to quit.	Trial lacked a control group. Helpful for project.
Glasgow et al. (2009) To determine effectiveness of smoking reduction program relative to usual care over 12-months. Also, assessed strength and cost of the program.	Randomized trial IV's: Intervention participants (telephone counselling + newsletters); Control participants (usual care) DV's: Reduction in # of cigarettes; Cigarettes per day smoked; Quit smoking.	320 adults, 18 years and older, currently smoking ≥ 10 cigarettes daily, scheduled for surgery or procedure between November 2004 & April 2006. Kaiser Permanente Colorado	Baseline, 3 months & 12 months: $\geq 50\%$ reduction in # of cigarettes smoked; # of cigarettes smoked per day; Quit smoking	Only one between group comparison was statistically significant (50% reduction of cigarettes smoked, intervention group). Control group showed improvement in # of cigarettes smoked, intervention group improved to a lesser extent. 6.5% of intervention participants quit by 12 months compared to 4.4% in control group.	Study shows feasibility of implementing large-scale smoke cessation program. Although results favored interventions over usual care, none were statistically significant at 12-month follow-up. Possibly due to contextual factors (e.g., \uparrow tobacco tax, statewide no smoking ordinance). Biochemical assessment may have influenced the control group. Exclusion of Spanish speaking smokers, high attrition rate, conducted in 1 setting. No NRT. Helpful for project
Newhall et al. (2017) To determine if brief smoke cessation interventions have measurable impact on	Pilot cluster randomized trial IV's: Intervention participants	156 participants from 8 vascular surgery practices throughout United States between September 1, 2014 & August 31, 2015.	Initial survey and 3-month follow-up survey	Intervention group expressed "a lot" or "some" interest in quitting (95.4% vs 85.7%, $p = 0.05$).	Smoke cessation counselling \uparrow patients' willingness to quit and \uparrow awareness of harmful effects of smoking.

Author/Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample/Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusions/Limitations Appropriateness
patient's attitudes toward smoking and if sustainable at 3 months.	(Counselling, medication, referral); Control participants (Counselling). DV's: Desire to quit; Nicotine dependence; Negative health effects of smoking.		Questions formulated using validated instruments. Questions included: desire for smoking cessation, nicotine, dependence, negative effects of smoking.	Intervention group more likely to acknowledge nicotine addiction (52.9 vs 48, $p = 0.006$) & negative effects of smoking (56.6 vs 50.6, $p = 0.001$). Follow-up survey: intervention group showed larger declines in nicotine dependence & negative health effects, suggesting robustness of the interventions at 3 months.	Baseline pack-year history differed between intervention & control groups. Survey delivered following intervention vs pre & post intervention. 15% of patients who did not quit smoking at follow-up did not fill out survey. Selection bias: those who enrolled, perhaps interested in quitting. Helpful for project.
Warner et al. (2011) Develop & test intervention in preoperative clinic facilitating telephone quitline use for smokers scheduled for elective surgery.	Randomized controlled trial IV's: Quitline facilitation intervention vs brief stop smoking intervention; Standard 5A's approach;	August 2007 & October 2009, 300 participants randomized, 149 quitline; 151 standard approach. Daily or someday smokers ≥ 18 years of age (> 100 cigarettes over lifetime).	Interventions: Advice to quit smoking for as long as possible prior to & following surgery (emphasis on morning of surgery), Description of quitline services, Provision of a quitline brochure & option of	29 of 149 (19.5%) quitline, 0 control group completed 1 st counselling session ($p = 0.0001$). Median # sessions 4. Point prevalence & continuous abstinence at 30 & 90 days higher in the quitline intervention;	Quitline effective in facilitating quitline use with approximately 1 out of 5 smokers accessing quitline services. Results from 1 preoperative clinic and may not generalize to other settings. Most patients seen 1 day prior to surgery, limiting

Author/Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample/Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusions/Limitations Appropriateness
	<p>DV's: Rate if quitline use;</p> <p>Smoking behavior at 30 & 90 days postoperatively.</p>	<p>Preoperative Evaluation Center at Mayo Clinic Rochester Minnesota.</p>	<p>faxed referral to quitline provider.</p> <p>Control condition: Advice to quit,</p> <p>Benefits of quitting relative to surgical outcomes,</p> <p>Techniques to assist in quit attempt, including quitline (no description),</p> <p>Brochure with quitline number.</p> <p>Difference between comparison & intervention: Later <u>facilitates</u> quitline use.</p>	<p>not statistically significant.</p>	<p>quitline use preoperatively & motivation to quit.</p> <p>Study not sufficiently powered to evaluate abstinence outcomes.</p> <p>Useful for project.</p>
<p>Robinson et al. (2012)</p> <p>Is TTM effective in promoting smoke cessation among adolescents?</p>	<p>CINAHL, Cochrane Library, Cochrane Clinical Trials Register, Psychological Abstracts & Sociological Abstracts.</p>	<p>6 RCT's.</p>	<p>English articles, peer reviewed (01/01/99 to 06/01/09), + landmark studies.</p> <p>Excluded: not RCT, observational studies or reviews; adults only, addressed other forms of tobacco use, focused on prevention,</p>	<p>Four studies significantly better quit rates in intervention arm vs. control arm (which sometimes used some guidance + pamphlet).</p>	<p>Interventions incorporating TTM can be used to effect change in adolescent smokers, hence promoting cessation.</p> <p>Additional trials may have been overlooked.</p> <p>Only ½ of trials recorded baseline stage of change</p>

Author/Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample/Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusions/Limitations Appropriateness
			<p>included a special population, did not reflect on TTM and/or measure cessation.</p> <p>Subjects ages 13 to 19 years</p>	<p>5 of 6 intervention groups quit rates > 12%</p> <p>6 of 6 intervention groups > quit rates than unaided teen rate (3% to 7 %).</p>	<p>limiting this study's ability to evaluate stage-based intervention.</p> <p>Helpful for project.</p>
<p>Yousefzaheh et al. (2016)</p> <p>Provide practical and multidisciplinary approach for implementing a perioperative smoke cessation program.</p>	<p>Review article</p> <p>Medline (January 1946 to May 2015) and EMBASE (January 1974 to May 205).</p>	<p>Studies on perioperative smoking cessation.</p> <p>Search strategy yielded 1717 articles, 95 included in the review.</p>	<p>English-language articles on human subjects.</p> <p>Exclusion criteria: duplicate publications; title, abstract & full text evaluation.</p>	<p>Brief interventions result in significant ↑ in abstinence rates.</p> <p>Strategies include: 5A's,</p> <p>Ask, Advise, Connect (to counselling resources), practical strategy, should be incorporated in perioperative setting.</p> <p>Brief counselling using TTM, promotes smoke cessation.</p> <p>Pharmacotherapy (NRT, Bupropion, Varenicline) significantly increases quit rates.</p>	<p>Brief interventions for tobacco use should be implemented in preoperative clinics to improve short-term surgical outcomes and long-term health outcomes as well as costs.</p> <p>Lack of conclusive evidence about safety of NRT before surgery.</p> <p>Would postponing surgery to implement cessation interventions improve postoperative outcomes, long term abstinence?</p> <p>Helpful for project.</p>

Author/Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample/Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusions/Limitations Appropriateness
				Directly connecting smokers to counselling resources results in 13-fold ↑ in treatment enrollment.	
<p>Zaki et al. (2008)</p> <p>Determine effectiveness of smoke cessation interventions provided to patients in preoperative clinic to promote cessation > 3 months following surgery.</p>	<p>Systematic review</p> <p>Cochrane Library (Issue 3, 2007), MEDLINE (January 1950 to September 2007), EMBASE (January 1974 to September 2007), CINAHL (January 1982 to September 2007).</p>	<p>Search yielded 2714 articles. Of these, 4 RCT's were considered for review, n = 610 patients.</p>	<p>Eligible for inclusion: RCT with parallel group design,</p> <p>Intervention (counselling, ± pharmacotherapy, literature, or post discharge follow-up) initiated in preoperative clinic to promote smoke cessation,</p> <p>included quit rates at 3, 6 & 12 months after surgery.</p> <p>Control intervention: usual care or advise only.</p> <p>Observational studies were excluded.</p>	<p>Interventions associated with a significantly higher cessation rate when compared to controls at 3 to 6-month follow-up.</p> <p>↑ chance of abstinence by nearly 60% within 3 to 6 months following surgery.</p> <p>One trial with 12-month follow-up did not show significant difference between intervention & control groups.</p>	<p>Suggest that smoke cessation interventions to include counselling and pharmacotherapy initiated in a preoperative clinic can ↑ likelihood of cessation within a 3 to 6-month period following surgery.</p> <p>While limitations relative to selected studies were discussed, no limitations relative to the systematic review were found.</p> <p>Helpful for project.</p>
<p>Minian et al. (2016)</p> <p>To explore what characteristics of</p>	<p>Phenomenological theoretical framework</p>	<p>23 female clients attended/participated in 1 of 4 focus groups.</p>	<p>Four focus groups (range 3 to 8/group).</p>	<p>Themes: Choice (flexible, client centered</p>	<p>Optimizing a program would include providing choices to enable women to identify services that work well for</p>

Author/Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample/Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusions/Limitations Appropriateness
treatment were of help and support while participating in a smoke cessation program, and what areas would be helpful to improve smoke cessation programming for women.		Female clients who sought treatment at an outpatient smoking cessation clinic in Toronto, Ontario between June 2012, and June 2013.	<p>Participants asked about: Past quit attempts, challenges they faced, thoughts about services, & suggestions to improve services.</p> <p>Sessions were audio recorded and student took notes.</p> <p>Themes identified using inductive process.</p>	<p>approach, meet specific needs), Free pharmacotherapy, Support (non-judgmental atmosphere, support groups, peer/outside support) Accessibility (evening/weekend hours), Communication (programming options) Women specific topics and groups (e.g., smoke cessation and pregnancy or menopause).</p>	<p>them. Free pharmacotherapy, nonjudgmental support, access to services and clarity of services available also contribute to program optimization.</p> <p>Women in attendance not representative of all women who seek treatment at clinic.</p> <p>Sample \geq 50 year of age.</p> <p>Focus questions not derived from theoretical framework.</p> <p>No guidelines to determine point of saturation, hence additional themes may have occurred.</p> <p>Same themes may emerge among men.</p> <p>Helpful for project.</p>
Warner et al. (2008) To determine attitudes & beliefs of preoperative patients and surgeons, anesthesiology providers regarding	Qualitative research approach	<p>Two categories of participants were recruited at the Mayo Clinic in Rochester Minnesota.</p> <p>Group one: A convenience sample (\geq</p>	<p>Semi-structured qualitative interview guide for patient interviews.</p> <p>A separate semi-structured guide was</p>	<p>Patient themes: Interest in quitting around time of surgery, view of physician's role important in cessation attempts,</p>	<p>Preoperative patients, as well as those who recently underwent surgery receptive to quitline use as an adjunct to smoke cessation interventions.</p>

Author/Purpose	Design/Key variables	Sample/Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusions/Limitations Appropriateness
smoke cessation interventions during the perioperative period.		18 years of age), n = 19, current smokers (at least 1 cigarette/day), scheduled for, or who had undergone surgery within 1 month. Group two: staff anesthesiologists & surgeons, n = 10.	developed for provider interviews. Interviews conducted in 2007. Interviews audiotaped & transcribed verbatim for analysis.	lack of knowledge regarding quitlines, poorly informed on benefits of cessation on surgical outcomes. Provider themes: Lack of knowledge regarding quitlines, Lack of time to deliver interventions, Interest in referring to quitlines if easily accomplished; willing to spend limited time learning (5 to 120 minutes, most < 30 minutes).	A lack of knowledge by perioperative patients, surgeons & anesthesiology providers regarding quitlines has led to their underutilization.

Note. SCI = smoke cessation intervention; TTM = transtheoretical model; PCP = primary care provider; NRT = nicotine replacement therapy; CINAHL = Cumulative Index to Nursing and Applied Health; Post-op = postoperative; Pre-op = preoperative; IV = independent variable; DV = dependent variable; G1 = group 1; G2 = group 2; MI = myocardial infarction; ACS-NSQIP = American College of Surgeons National Surgical Quality Improvement Program; NRT = nicotine replacement therapy; GA = general anesthesia; PNA = pneumonia; CPD = cigarettes smoked per day; ICD-9 = International Classification of Diseases, Ninth Edition; ICD-10 = International Classification of Diseases, Tenth Edition.

Table 3

Smoke Cessation Before Surgery

Author/Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusions/Limitations Appropriateness
<p>Bottorff et al. (2015)</p> <p>Determine knowledge about perioperative risks of smoking, proportion of smokers who quit prior to surgery, if health care provider advice received & patient knowledge/use of resources for smoke cessation for adult smokers who received elective surgery.</p>	<p>Cross-sectional design.</p> <p>Survey of current smokers.</p> <p>Variables of interest:</p> <p>Knowledge of perioperative risks of smoking;</p> <p>Patient smoking cessation;</p> <p>Health care provider advice/assistance;</p> <p>Use of resources.</p>	<p>161 adult cigarette smokers (≥ 1 cigarette in the 6 months prior to surgery).</p> <p>2 regional hospitals in northern British Columbia.</p>	<p><i>Tobacco use</i> questions derived from measures used in national surveys & developed by experts (questions provided).</p> <p>Included questions on <i>Advice and support & Smoking cessation resources</i>.</p> <p>2 measures to describe patient sample: Smoking stages of change scale; Fagerstrom Test for Nicotine Dependence.</p> <p>Measure to assess awareness of smoking-related perioperative complications (Likert response scale).</p>	<p>Quit durations predominately short: 7.5% of patients quit smoking & 38.8% reduced smoking 8 weeks prior to surgery.</p> <p>Only ½ of patients advised by health care provider to quit prior to surgery.</p> <p>5% of patients used resources to support smoke cessation.</p> <p>Only ½ of these patients aware that continued smoking ↑'d surgical risks.</p>	<p>Knowledge about perioperative risks of smoking and use of smoke cessation resources are low.</p> <p>Results suggest a need for provision of information about perioperative risks of smoking which could provide further incentive to quit.</p> <p>Limitations of generalizability when describing retrospective experiences of a regionally based sample.</p> <p>Responses subject to recall bias; smoking patterns based on self-report.</p> <p>Research oriented to 2 months prior to surgery.</p> <p>Useful for my project</p>
Shi et al. (2010)	Longitudinal study	5498 current smokers.	Survey with follow up interviews every 2 years.	2444 out of 5489 individuals (44.5 %) quit smoking.	Having major surgery is associated with ↑'d quit

Author/Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusions/Limitations Appropriateness
<p>To determine association between selected surgical procedures and smoke cessation.</p>	<p>IV's: Type of surgery (heart; cancer; joint outpatient).</p> <p>DV's: Incidence of cessation associated with procedure;</p> <p>Annual number of quitters in US associated with procedure.</p> <p>Annual number of quitters in US attributable to procedure.</p>	<p>Age of cohort members in 1992 was 57 ± 10 years. A sample 70 years and older was enrolled in 1993, and another group enrolled in 1998, age group falling in between 1st 2 cohorts.</p> <p>Analyses performed of longitudinal biennial survey data (1992 – 2004) from nationally representative Health & Retirement Study (HRS) of U.S. adults > 50 years of age.</p>	<p>Incidence of 3 types of major surgery: Heart, cancer & joint.</p> <p>Number of smokers who quit smoking relative to surgical procedures.</p>	<p>Incidence of those who quit following major surgery 20.6/100 person years & 10.2/100 after outpatient procedures.</p> <p>~ 8% of quit events attributed to surgical procedures.</p>	<p>events (smoke cessation) in older people living in U.S.</p> <p>This information supports the idea that surgery is a good time to discuss smoke cessation.</p> <p>Data relies on self-reported health events & smoking events.</p> <p>Only 4 categories of surgery available.</p> <p>HRS enrolled adults > 50, hence does not reflect younger adults.</p> <p>Other confounding variables not analyzed.</p> <p>Some patients may have received tobacco interventions; not likely all quit events spontaneous.</p> <p>Helpful for project.</p>
<p>Azodi et al. (2009)</p> <p>Investigate efficacy of pre-op smoke cessation program</p>	<p>Randomized clinical trial.</p> <p>IV: Intensive smoking intervention</p>	<p>117 adult cigarette smokers (> 2 cigarettes per day during at least 1 year prior to inclusion)</p>	<p>Smoking status & tobacco consumption were recorded weekly for intervention group.</p>	<p>Intention to treat analysis: 36% of patients in G1 & 2% in G2 completely abstinent 3 weeks</p>	<p>Successful smoking cessation can be accomplished by providing intervention only 4 weeks prior to surgery, especially</p>

Author/Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusions/Limitations Appropriateness
<p>starting 4 weeks pre-op & ending 4 weeks post-op for adult smokers.</p> <p>Study how patient related characteristics affect the likelihood of long-term abstinence.</p>	<p>program = G1; Standard care = G2.</p> <p>DV's: Perioperative abstinence; Abstinence after 1 year.</p>	<p>4 university affiliated hospitals in Stockholm Sweden.</p>	<p>All patients completed questionnaire about smoking; repeat CO measurement 2-3 weeks postop.</p> <p>Long term smoking status assessed by questionnaire @ 12 months postop.</p> <p>Fagerström Test for Nicotine Dependence.</p>	<p>prior to surgery to 4 weeks following surgery ($p < 0.001$). Corresponding per <i>protocol</i> data were 40% and 2% ($p < 0001$).</p> <p>Abstinence ↑'d (protocol analysis) from 40% at 3 weeks pre-op to 58% at 1 week pre-op.</p> <p>Abstinence after 1 year was 33% for G1 vs. 15% for G2 ($p = 0.03$). Corresponding values for <i>per protocol</i> analysis was 35% and 17% ($p = 0.04$).</p> <p>Low nicotine dependence & obesity significantly associated with success in smoking cessation.</p>	<p>given many surgical conditions do not allow longer pre-op intervention.</p> <p>Shorter interventions likely more achievable and affordable.</p> <p>Intervention highly effective in reducing post-op complications.</p> <p>Smoking status at 1 year was not verified by CO measurement; lack of verification may overestimate probability of abstinence at 1 year.</p> <p>Study not designed to investigate predictors of successful smoke cessation. Due to low rate of recruitment, study terminated before planned number of patients were recruited. Hence, small sample size; risk of type II error.</p> <p>Self-selection (cohort more willing to quit than smokers in general).</p>

Author/Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusions/Limitations Appropriateness
					Useful for my project.
<p>Mills et al. (2011)</p> <p>Determine if there is an optimal time period to stop smoking prior to surgery.</p>	<p>Systematic review & Meta-analysis</p> <p>MEDLINE, EMBASE, Cochrane CENTRAL, AMED, CINAHL, TOXNET, Development and Reproductive Toxicology, Hazardous Substances Databank, PsycINFO, Web of Science, ScienceDirect and Ingenta (from inception to September 2009).</p>	<p>6 randomized trials and 15 observational studies.</p>	<p>Period of cessation (< 4 weeks & > 4 weeks),</p> <p>Postoperative complications (total complications),</p> <p>Secondary outcomes, specific complications: (wound healing, pulmonary or respiratory, mortality, length of stay).</p>	<p>RTC's showed a relative risk reduction of 41% (95% CI, $p = .01$) for prevention of postoperative complications.</p> <p>Each week of cessation ↑'d magnitude of effect by 19%.</p> <p>> 4 weeks of cessation has significantly greater treatment effect than shorter trials (< 4 weeks).</p> <p>Observational studies: longer vs. shorter periods of cessation, 20% average ↓ in total complications.</p>	<p>Each additional week of smoke cessation prior to surgery results in a significant decrease in smoking related post-operative complications.</p> <p>Limitations in analysis related to:</p> <p>Heterogeneous reporting of outcomes,</p> <p>Inconsistent reporting of past smoking status,</p> <p>Differences in study designs across observational studies.</p> <p>Helpful for project.</p>
<p>Thomsen et al. (2009)</p> <p>To explore effect of smoke cessation interventions delivered preoperatively on postoperative complications as well as smoke cessation following surgery.</p>	<p>Systematic review</p> <p>Pubmed, Cochran Library, Embase, CINAHL</p>	<p>Eleven RCT's (2002 - 2008), 1194 patients.</p> <p>Daily smokers, ≥ 18 year of age.</p>	<p>Smoke cessation intervention (intensive, medium intensity and less intensive)</p> <p>Postoperative complications (up to 30 days following surgery)</p>	<p>Overall, interventions significantly reduced postoperative complications ($p < .001$).</p> <p>Intensive interventions ↑'d preoperative & postoperative (up to 12</p>	<p>Suggests that patients who undergo intensive smoke cessation intervention ≥ 4 weeks prior to surgery (+NRT) benefit with respect to ↓'d postoperative complications.</p>

Author/Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusions/Limitations Appropriateness
			Preoperative and postoperative (from DOS to 12 months) smoke cessation.	months) cessation rates. Effects of medium & less intensive interventions were not significant (postoperative complications and cessation at 3 and 6 months). May have been underpowered.	Medium & low intensive interventions varied considerably. Definitions of smoke cessation also varied. Judgement of complications somewhat subjective. Helpful for project.

Note. Post-op = postoperative; Pre-op = preoperative; IV = independent variable; DV = dependent variable; G1 = group 1; G2 = group 2; MI = myocardial infarction; ACS-NSQIP = American College of Surgeons National Surgical Quality Improvement Program; NRT = nicotine replacement therapy; GA = general anesthesia; PNA = pneumonia; CPD = cigarettes smoked per day; ICD-9 = International Classification of Diseases, Ninth Edition; ICD-10 = International Classification of Diseases, Tenth Edition; DOS = day of surgery; SCI = smoke cessation intervention; TTM = Transtheoretical model; PCP = primary care provider; NRT = nicotine replacement therapy; CINAHL = Cumulative Index to Nursing and Applied Health.

APPENDIX B SMOKE CESSATION ALGORITHM

APPENDIX C

SAMPLE SCRIPT FOR SMOKING CESSATION

Ask:

- Do you smoke?
- How many cigarettes do you smoke a day?

(If a patient has recently quit: Congratulations! I would like to encourage you as you continue your journey as a former smoker and appreciate the benefits of being smoke free.)

Advise:

- Quitting would be of great benefit for your health.

Assess:

- Have you thought about quitting?
- Smoking can increase your risk of heart, lung, and wound healing complications during and after surgery.
- Quitting as early as 24 hours prior to surgery results in an immediate reduction in nicotine and carbon monoxide in the bloodstream (reducing blood pressure, heart rate and improving oxygen levels), thereby decreasing complications during and after surgery.
- Wound and respiratory complications can be reduced by quitting three to four weeks prior to surgery.
- Many smokers use surgery as a time to consider quitting for good.

- **It sounds like you are not ready to quit soon.** Let me provide you with some educational materials that may be helpful whenever you decide to quit.

Assist:

- **You're interested in quitting** in the next 30 days. That's great!
- Here are some things you can do in the meantime:
 1. Instead of lighting up in the morning, you may want to go for a walk.
 2. You may wish to try gum or carrot sticks in place of a cigarette.
 3. Try to avoid other smokers if possible.
- I'm going to provide you with some educational materials that may be of help.

Arrange:

- This is what we can do for you (i.e., counselling services or quitline).

APPENDIX D

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY AND PERIOPERATIVE RISKS OF SMOKING

1. Cardiovascular
 - a. Nicotine, which increases sympathetic activity and carbon monoxide which displaces oxygen on hemoglobin, can elevate blood pressure and heart rate (Benowitz & Burbank, 2016; Gourgiotis et al., 2011). Cigarette smoke accelerates atherosclerosis.
 - b. Surgery and anesthesia increase demands on the heart which can lead to cardiovascular complications.
2. Pulmonary
 - a. Smoking damages the mucus transport mechanism within the airways resulting in impaired mucus transport, airway hyperactivity, and susceptibility to infection or pneumonia (Yousefzadeh et al., 2016).
 - b. This may result in prolonged mechanical ventilation and/or reintubation following surgery/anesthesia.
3. Wound healing
 - a. Toxins in cigarette smoke work together to negatively affect tissue perfusion, oxygenation, and wound healing. Nicotine is a vasoconstrictor, thereby reducing blood flow to microvascular beds (Benowitz & Burbank, 2016; Yousefzadeh et al., 2016).
 - b. Complications include poor or delayed wound healing, dehiscence, infection, and repeat surgery (Khullar & Maa, 2012).
4. Increased length of stay

Benefits of Quitting

1. Immediate reduction in carboxyhemoglobin and nicotine levels in the blood stream which can improve hemodynamics prior to surgery and anesthesia (Lauerman, 2008).
2. Postoperative respiratory complications can be reduced with at least four weeks of smoke cessation prior to surgery. Wound-healing complications can be decreased with three to four weeks of smoke cessation prior to surgery (Wong et al., 2012).
3. Smoke cessation decreases the risk of developing a variety of cancers and diseases including lung cancer, coronary artery disease, cerebral vascular disease, peripheral vascular disease, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (Khullar & Maa, 2012; Siu, 2015).

4. Smokers with these conditions may appreciate some reversal of the pathological effects of smoking by quitting prior to surgery (Yousefzadeh et al., 2016).

APPENDIX E

GUIDE FOR SMOKING CESSATION PATIENT EDUCATION MATERIALS

Go to *Clinical References & Patient Instructions* tab.

In the search window type: “Smoking Cessation.”

Precontemplation, Contemplation

SMOKE FREE, BENEFITS OF LIVING (ENGLISH)

SMOKE, WHY DO YOU (ENGLISH)

SMOKING CESSATON

Preparation

SMOKE FREE, BENEFITS OF LIVING (ENGLISH)

SMOKE, WHY DO YOU (ENGLISH)

SMOKING CESSATON

SMOKING, GETTING SUPPORT FOR QUITTING (ENGLISH)

SMOKING, PLANNING TO QUIT (ENGLISH)

Action, Maintenance

SMOKE-FREE, STAYING (ENGLISH)

SMOKING WITHDRAWAL, COPING WITH (ENGLISH)

APPENDIX F

DATA COLLECTION SHEET

Date _____ Patient Age _____ Male / Female
 Ethnicity _____ Diagnosis (reason for surgery) _____

Current smoker

Cigarettes Pipe Cigar

Number of years of smoking _____

Ready to quit (within month)? Yes No

Counselling provided? Yes No

Educational materials provided? Yes No

Card/Brochure provided? Yes No

Referred to: Center for Health Promotion

California Smoker's Helpline

Currently receiving care/treatment? Yes No

Recent smoker (within 12 months)

Number of years of smoking _____

Encouragement or support given? Yes No

Educational materials provided? Yes No

